

Integration of national services into the ELIXIR compute platform

A proof of concept

Authors: Gerben Venekamp (SURF), Christine Staiger (DTL)

Introduction

Many European infrastructures are currently developing own data and compute services while at the same time leveraging national services and integrating them with their framework. To grant access to users those infrastructures need to identify, i.e. authenticate, and authorise individuals and to this end build different Authentication and Authorisation Infrastructures (AAI). Those AAIs are not only built and operated on international, European level but also on national level by so called local National Research and Education Networks (NRENs). This could potentially create competing AAIs and hinder the integration between the actual data and compute services.

Users would like to have easy access to the services they need and access them with one identity, preferably their home/University identity (see Figure 1). Service Providers (SPs) in that respect are no different, they would like to have easy access to the AAIs. The challenge is to connect the different AAIs in such a way that it does not get into the way of the users and also facilitates the SP. The vision of ELIXIR is to have one login to access all the services of the ELIXIR platforms, independent from the country of origin or the country by which the service is operated.

To this point ELIXIR and other EU AAIs favour that each service provider integrates the respective AAI into their authentication-authorisation mechanism. This procedure will potentially lead to a lot of overhead work for service providers who will be burdened not only with the technical implementation and integration, but also with the attribute mappings.

In this work we explore how an AAI from a European project can be integrated with a national AAI which then in turn is integrated with the national services. By this approach service providers will not be burdened with the integration of many different EU projects' AAI. We base our work on the infrastructure and services

provided by ELIXIR and the Dutch NREN SURF. Both ELIXIR and SURF comply with the BluePrint Architecture (BPA) as developed by the AARC project [1].

Figure 1: A user accesses many different services potentially offered by different countries with one identity.

Integration between a European AAI and a national AAI

The Dutch NREN, SURF, is exploring and building a new AAI infrastructure (Science Collaboration Zone (SCZ)[2]) to not only identify users but also to provide users and SPs with a way to create collaborations (user groups) which then can be pushed to several service providers. Integrating SCZ and the ELIXIR AAI offers the big advantage that not every single service has to independently integrate the ELIXIR AAI into their authentication-authorisation mechanism (see Figure 2). It is done once on the national level and service providers can decide whether they accept users with ELIXIR credentials and attributes.

To facilitate research between national researchers and peers from other countries, service providers need to be able to grant access to researchers from outside their national borders, i.e. in our case we want to enable Dutch service providers to grant access to any researcher who holds an ELIXIR identity. However, as stated above, services that the users would like to access, are not necessarily connected to the ELIXIR AAI, but rather to a national one. In order to understand what all this entails two AAIs are naively connected, i.e. the ELIXIR AAI and SCZ. The deliverable will present how a national AAI, namely SCZ and a European AAI, namely the ELIXIR AAI were integrated and what a typical user would experience when accessing Dutch services with an ELIXIR identity. Based on these findings the shortcomings are discussed and possible solutions are presented.

Figure 2: The Dutch e-infrastructure offers several services which users with an ELIXIR identity would like to access. The services come from different institutes, but are connected to the Dutch federation (SCZ).

Use case description - Setting the scene

In this proof of concept we would like to show that the envisioned integration can support both, web based services and non-web based services. After the integration users with an ELIXIR ID should be able to access: 1) a service to create virtual machines (SURFsara Research Cloud) and 2) two different VMs directly provided by two different cloud providers namely Research Cloud and the cloud service at the Rijksuniversiteit Groningen (see Figure 3). In the latter case the users would use a feature of the national AAI solution to manage RSA keys and automatically pull public keys from SCZ to single VM instances.

In our setup, both VMs in the different cloud environments have been configured to use LDAP for user login and the SSH configuration has been adapted to accept authorised public SSH keys from LDAP. SCZ maintains a master LDAP and provisions multiple client LDAPs from the master LDAP. Both SURF and RUG have their own unique partial copy of that master LDAP. Hence, we use that setup to facilitate two different Service Providers (SPs) which ensures that only information that belong to the SP is actually visible to that SP and only that SP. However, the users' attributes contained within each LDAP must be harmonised between the two LDAP servers. Here the national AAI SCZ plays the role of harmonising users' attributes between service providers. During the integration with other AAIs like ELIXIR, SCZ will already map attributes coming from ELIXIR to its own attributes. Subsequently, SPs can import those attributes and grant authorised access.

Figure 3. A user logs in to SCZ. The identity is checked by SCZ through the integration with the ELIXIR AAI. Subsequently, the user can employ SCZ as a service to store and manage extra attributes like public SSH keys. All attributes, coming from ELIXIR and the additional attributes, are provided to the respective services, here two virtual machines which pull users' attributes from SCZ's master LDAP.

Connecting ELIXIR to SCZ

Technically connecting the two AAls is not difficult. Both AAls employ a hub and spoke model also known as proxy and thus connecting the two proxies is all that is required. Since both, ELIXIR and SCZ, use the SAML 2.0 with the Web Browser SSO Profile [3], the two proxies can be connected using SAML which facilitates the establishment of a trust relationship between SCZ as an IdP and the ELIXIR AAI as an identity consumer or SP. To this end SAML provides metadata for these two types of entities which is exchanged and allows for the recognition of an entity. By signing this metadata the authenticity of the data is ensured.

Figure 3: Connecting two proxies by metadata exchange

Figure 4 shows how the different parties involved, i.e. IdP, SP and proxies, are connected. IdP and SP know how to connect through the SAML protocol. As stated before, a proxy is in its most basic form nothing more than both an IdP and SP. This makes it for an SP quite simple to connect to a proxy as it basically sees just an IdP. It does not know it is talking to a proxy. For an IdP it is the same, all it sees is an SP. In Figure 4, the orange coloring is for the IdP functionality and green is that for the SP. There it can be seen that orange and green are always connected and that, in theory, one could use as many proxies as one can think of.

Figure 4: Proxies are composed out of an IdP and an SP. Depicted is the flow from the SP through the proxies to the IdP and back to the SP again.

Challenges of Integrating Proxies

While the technical integration of two proxies is easy, the user experience during the authentication step prior to accessing a service suffers from some technical characteristics of the established chain of trust. Let's assume for the moment that a user would like to access some service at an SP. Figure 5 shows the user flow. In this figure, the different steps that a user has to take are numbered from 1 through 13.

1. Through the webbrowser the user accesses the service at <https://service.example.org/> (see Figure 6)
2. The SP, e.g. SURFsara, does not know who is trying to access the service and redirects the user to SCZ to authenticate the user.
3. SCZ itself does not know the user, but shows an HTML page listing all known IdPs. The user selects his IdP from that list, in our case ELIXIR. (see Figure 7)
4. SCZ redirects the user to the ELIXIR AAI to authenticate the user.
5. The ELIXIR AAI in turn lists all known IdPs. The user now selects his home IdP, here SURFsara. (see Figure 8)
6. The user is redirected to the selected IdP, here SURFsara..
7. At his home IdP the user authenticates with his credentials, i.e. username and password. (see Figure 9)
8. Assuming the authentication was successful, the user is redirected back to the ELIXIR AAI along with released user attributes from the IdP.
9. ELIXIR now holding a valid user needs the user's consent for sending attributes to the SP. (see Figure 11)
10. If the user agrees, ELIXIR redirect the user back to the SP, which in this case is SCZ.
11. SCZ now holds a valid user and asks for consent for sending attributes to the SP. (see Figure 12)
12. If the user agrees, SCZ redirects the user to the SP, which is SURFsara, with the attributes that SCZ releases.
13. If the correct attributes are received by the SP, the authenticated user is granted access to the service (see Figure 13).

Figure 5: User flow. User logs in at a service, goes through two proxies and is redirected back to the originating service after having performed a successful authentication at its home institute.

The above flow, although technically sound, has a number of shortcomings for the user. Firstly, users will most likely encounter double asked questions, especially when logging in for the first time with a new service. As indicated above, users need to select an IdP twice in the whole workflow, which might be confusing. Secondly, users have to give consent twice, once at the ELIXIR AAI and once at the SCZ AAI which might be seen as overhead and be confusing, fostering mistrust in the authentication mechanism itself. The Appendix shows a number of screenshots which the user will encounter.

Registering at both SCZ and ELIXIR

The shortcomings for users do not end with having to select an IdP twice and give consent twice. Users must not only be known by the IdP but also at both proxies. Figure 4 shows the composed behaviour of proxies and just like an IdP releases attributes, so must a proxy. This feature can be used in the case where an IdP does not provide sufficient attributes or additional attributes which an SP would be needed. The user's public SSH key is an example. In turn, this means that users must be known at the proxy and thus must have an account where the proxy can keep track of all the user attributes. Next to that, users must be able to manage a few of their attributes at the proxy, like their public SSH keys, and thus registering at the proxy is necessary. In the case of connecting two proxies it unfortunately means having two accounts.

One trait proxies often have is that they handout a new identity for users which differ from the identity they received from their IdP. This is done on purpose. In the proxy scenario, IdPs do not know to which SPs the proxies are connected and thus proxies could potentially send user attributes to any of the connected SPs. To provide a bit more security, proxies issue a new identity based on the original one and create a new attribute which denotes the community the user comes from. Service providers do not need to know the exact and original identity of a user, but they need sufficiently fine-grained information on the users' community, which is provided by the proxy. In our case the ELIXIR AAI denotes de ELIXIR community, which is sufficient for the two test service providers to authorise users.

Recommendations

The above describes the users' flow to authenticate with a service through the connections of two AAI. Although it works on a technical level, users still experiences a lot of confusion and thus the technical solution needs to be improved.

The first problem users encountered in this test setup were several pages asking them to select an identity provider (multiple WAYFs). So-called 'IdP hinting' can alleviate that problem . Through IdP hinting the SP knows which IdP is valid for the current user who tries to access the service. In that way the discovery, or WAYF, page can be skipped. To be more concrete: the SP is still connected to the SCZ, but when the user is directed to SCZ, SCZ is being informed which is user's anticipated IdP. In this case it will be ELIXIR and SCZ skips the discovery page and redirect to the ELIXIR AAI instead. It is at ELIXIR where the users select their IdP, e.g. their home organisation.

Another shortcoming for the users experience and also the maintenance of the integration is the release of attributes. It would be very advantageous if the integration could be done in a way such that the national AAI, SCZ, is transparent to the user. I.e. the users log in via the ELIXIR AAI and SCZ passes their attributes to the service providers instead of releasing new attributes. In such a scenario users would still need to be known at both the national and the international AAI. Additional attributes, like the public SSH key which users configured in the ELIXIR AAI could be reused. Such a scenario can be achieved if the trust relationship between the two AAIs is extended such that the SCZ, i.e. the AAI which the SP is connected to, would pass on the received attributes verbatim.

Further improvement to the scenario above include automatic user registration. This mitigates the different accounts, one for each AAI, users must create and maintain. In case SCZ would transparently accept ELIXIR users, SCZ would be truly transparent to the user. This would however require significant changes, not only on the technical level to operate the AAI , but also in legal policies. that provides some major challenge when trying to extend our use case scenario to different national AAIs and also to different international AAIs. One huge legal framework has to be built to allow the integration between AAIs on European level to allow for scientific collaboration across different EU projects.

Conclusions

By coupling two AAIs, ELIXIR and SCZ, we have demonstrated that it is possible to have ELIXIR users make use of the services provided by SURFsara or the Rijksuniversiteit Groningen, through connecting the two services to a national AAI and not directly to the ELIXIR AAI. However, our work also showed that although technically feasible, the legal framework still needs to be adjusted and the user experience needs to be improved. In the current setup, users need to register at both AAI, are redirected to the IdP discovery (WAYF) twice and need give consent for sending attributes to the consumer (service provider) for both AAIs. In other words, there are a lot of screens involved and to the user some screens fulfill the same purpose, making them look redundant which shows the great potential to confuse users.

The users' experience can be improved on the one hand by IdP hinting at the SP side, thus leaving out one discovery page. On the other hand, if SCZ can be made transparent to the users, no interaction with SCZ would be required anymore. Thus, further improving the user experience.

Final words

Before we started this proof of concept, we expected a suboptimal user experience and this PoC has indeed confirmed this. Offering this in its current state is not something we wish to do and thus it will be discontinued as planned. Next to the user experience, we need to work on a legal framework for integrating both AAls. This allows for a smoother user experience in the future. Once these two issues are solved, the connection can be reestablished.

References

- [1] <https://aarc-project.eu/architecture/>
- [2] <https://wiki.surfnet.nl/display/SCZ/Science+Collaboration+Zone+Home>
- [3] https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/SAML_2.0#Web_Browser_SSO_Profile

Appendix

Screenshot of the screens a user will typically encounter when it wants to access a service.

Figure 6: Logging into COmanage starts a SAML flow just as any other service would.

Figure 7: SCZ asks the user select an IdP which is able to authenticate the user. This is the discovery phase for SCZ. Here the user should not choose its home organisation, but rather ELIXIR as it is that identify the user wants to use.

Figure 8: ELIXIR needs to know what home organisation is able to authenticate the user and enters the discovery phase for ELIXIR. It is here where the user must select its home institute.

Figure 9: After the user has selected its home institute, it is redirected there where the user is asked to provide its credentials in order to authenticate the user.

Figure 10: This is probably an additional step needed, because we are in the test environment of ELIXIR and this message should not appear once SCZ is connected to the production environment.

Figure 11: Before ELIXIR redirects the user the SP, which is SCZ in our case, ELIXIR need user consent and shows the attributes it will send.

Figure 12: Before SCZ will redirect the user to the requested service it will need user consent for sending the shown attributes.

Figure 13: The final step in the SAML flow is that the user is granted access to the service. In our case we started by trying to access COmanage.